

These values show that Cu^{2+} has a general preference for coordination with nitrogen in preference to oxygen and this is in keeping with its classification as "intermediate" acid in the hard-soft system. The preference for mixed-donors over either all nitrogen or all oxygen donors is obvious. In the case of $[\text{Cu}(\text{lact})(\text{ox})]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{ox})(\text{gly})]$, both have uninegative charge. Hence the only reason for the enhanced value of $\log X$ for $[\text{Cu}(\text{ox})(\text{gly})]$ is due to hetero donors. Another example is the pair $[\text{Cu}(\text{lact})(\text{en})]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{gly})]$ each with unipositive charge.

The 1:1 copper-oxalate complex is highly insoluble and is precipitated under pH-titration conditions. In the present studies involving the use of spectrophotometry and polarography it has been found possible to avoid the precipitation of $[\text{Cu}(\text{ox})]$ and these techniques have been found to be advantageous in the study of Cu^{2+} systems containing oxalate as a ligand.

In the case of lactate complexes, the studies indicate the coordination of the hydroxyl group in its unionised form, though such coordination is weaker than in its deprotonated form. Such participation may be important in biological processes such as metal-enzyme action, as it allows a rapid rearrangement of the complexes necessary for the enzyme to act as a catalyst.

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α -Iodoacetoacetanilide and Its Metal Chelates

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Manuscript received 12 May 1980, revised 10 September 1980,
accepted 29 January 1981

EARLIER studies using α -bromo and α -chloroacetoacetanilides^{1,2} have revealed that, contrary to expectation, these ligands have enhanced chelating ability than acetoacetanilide. In this connection it was of interest to examine the chelating tendency of α -iodoacetoacetanilide. However, only a very few of its com-

plexes could be obtained analytically pure, since the complexes are mostly insoluble in all common solvents.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by adding to a hot solution of acetoacetanilide (17.7 g, 0.1 mol) in ethanol (50 ml), iodine (10 g, 0.04 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) followed by iodic acid (3.44 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in hot water (5 ml). The mixture was refluxed over a water-bath for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled in a freezing mixture and the yellow precipitate formed³ filtered quickly, and washed successively with water, ice-cold aqueous ethanol, and petroleum ether, till the washings were colourless. The product was recrystallised from ethanol, when 17.6 g (58% yield, m.p. 126°) of the pure material were obtained. Found C, 39.51; H, 3.23; N, 4.51%. Calculated percentages, C, 39.62; H, 3.30; N, 4.62%. Infrared spectrum (Nujol mull) showed strong carbonyl bands at 1730 and 1660 cm^{-1} , and a medium intensity broad N-H stretching band at 3240 cm^{-1} . N.M.R. spectrum in CDCl_3 showed that the product is indeed α -iodoacetoacetanilide. Four absorptions, as expected, were observed at 0.78 τ (broad singlet for NH), 2.5 τ (multiplet for C_6H_5), 4.8 τ (singlet for α -CH) and 7.4 τ (singlet for CH_3). Integrated intensities agreed with the number of different kinds of hydrogen present.

Metal chelates of the ligand were prepared as follows :

Beryllium(II) chelate : To a stirred hot solution of ligand (0.02 mol) in ethanol (200 ml), a hot solution of beryllium sulphate pentahydrate (0.01 mol) in water (10 ml) was added dropwise. The pH of the mixture was adjusted to 6-6.5 with dilute ammonia, continued stirring for 1 hr, and the precipitated complex filtered.

Copper(II) chelate : A solution of ligand (0.02 mol) in methanol (100 ml) was added to a stirred methanolic solution (50 ml) of copper(II) acetate hydrate (0.01 mol). After continued stirring for 2 hr, the crystalline precipitate formed was filtered.

Chromium(III) chelate : Chromium(III) chloride hexahydrate (0.005 mol) was dissolved in water (50 ml) containing urea (10 g). The ligand (0.03 mol, excess) in ethanol (50 ml) was added and the mixture refluxed for 9 hr. The precipitated complex was filtered hot.

Iron(III) chelate : An aqueous solution (50 ml) of iron(III) chloride (0.01 mol) containing sodium acetate trihydrate (3 g) was added to an ethanolic solution (100 ml) of ligand (0.03 mol), and the mixture stirred for 1 hr. The solution was then concentrated to 75 ml, and subsequently cooled in ice. The amorphous residue separated turned crystalline on trituration with petroleum ether.

Manganese, cobalt and nickel complexes : Aqueous solutions of manganese(II), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) salts yielded only insoluble and intractable crude materials with alcoholic solution of the ligand.

TABLE I—METAL CHELATES OF α -IODOACETOACETANILIDE

Complex	Solvent used for recrystallisation	Yield (%)	m. p. (°C)	Magnetic moment (B. M.)	Molecular Weight†	Molar Conductance $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$	Analytical Data‡		
							C (%)	H (%)	N (%)
BeL ₂	*	44	**	D			38.98 (39.15)	2.92 (2.94)	4.11 (4.57)
CuL ₂	*	50	130	1.73			35.25 (39.96)	2.32 (2.69)	3.81 (4.19)
CrL ₂	*	25	220 d	3.82			37.19 (37.59)	2.12 (2.82)	4.28 (4.38)
FeL ₂	Benzene-pet-ether	28	**	5.92	985 (962)	6.82	36.98 (37.44)	4.62 (2.80)	4.19 (4.36)

D—Diamagnetic

d-decomposes

* Insoluble

** Not melting or visibly decomposing upto 360°

† Calculated values in brackets.

Attempted synthesis of cobalt(III) chelate was unsuccessful, since aeration of the reaction mixture containing cobalt(II) and ligand, caused liberation of iodine.

Only the iron(III) complex could be recrystallised, and was found nonconducting in methanol. Its monomeric nature was revealed by its molecular weight, determined cryoscopically in benzene. Other complexes were first washed with water and then repeatedly with hot alcohol and acetone. Details of the complexes obtained analytically pure are brought out in Table 1. Infrared spectra of the complexes (Nujol mull) showed that, in conformity with the expected β -amidoenolate structure of the ligand moiety^{1,2}, the carbonyl bands are lowered to about 1565 and 1550 cm^{-1} , and the N-H stretching frequency raised to about 3300 cm^{-1} , in the metal chelates. As compared to the spectra of the corresponding metal chelates of (unsubstituted) acetoacetanilide, the upward shift of the N-H stretching band is less, probably because weak inter- or intramolecular hydrogen-bonding of N-H with the halogen, occurs also in the metal chelates.

A Toshniwal conductivity bridge, Gouy-type balance, Perkin-Elmer 137 infrared spectrometer and Varian A 60 D N.M.R. spectrometer were used for conductance, magnetic and spectral measurements.

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Complexation Reaction of Iron(III) with Salicyloylhydrazide

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Manuscript received 4 March 1980, revised 6 October 1980,
accepted 29 January 1981

THE complexation of salicyloylhydrazide with manganese¹, titanium² and vanadium³ has been reported in literature. This complexation is useful in the gravimetric determination of titanium in the industrial samples. The reddish brown coloured complex of salicyloylhydrazide with Fe(III) in 80% (v/v) aqueous ethanol has been studied and reported in the present communication.

Experimental

The salicyloylhydrazide was dissolved in absolute alcohol to get 0.02 M solution. The Fe(III) solution was prepared in double distilled water from ferric chloride (BDH 'AnalaR') and standardized to 0.1 M solution⁴. The absorbance was measured with Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 20-spectrophotometer in 80% (v/v) aqueous ethanol at pH 3.2 keeping the temperature at $35 \pm 1^\circ$. The pH was adjusted to 3.2 by adding sodium hydroxide or hydrochloric acid and it was measured with 'Systronics' pH-meter using glass and calomel electrodes.

Results and Discussion

In order to select the wavelength for the maximum absorbance by the complex 8×10^{-4} moles of Fe(III)